

INCOMPATIBLE COMMISSIONS

—Desperately looking for a common language

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Extended Abstract

(For *Dirty Documents and Unspoken Aesthetics* or *Controversies and Confessions* themes)

Most southwestern European nations—in stark contrast to their northern counterparts—require that residential designs submitted for building permits be prepared by licensed architects, albeit with slight variations from country to country. This legal framework has created, for the general public, an obligation to hire an architect and to engage—often for the first time—in a process of technical communication and aesthetic decision-making.

This paper will detail such experience as a local architect in a rural territory. After many years abroad I returned to the place where I had spent my childhood summers, receiving a commission to design a house for clients from that community. In the first meeting an ethical problem was identified. My set of references for what a house in that context could be was highly contrasting with theirs. Where I had anticipated a narrative of folk forms, regional materials, the use of natural light, and elaborated spatial relationships—such as varied floor levels, and room to room proportions—my clients, born and raised there, were expecting almost the opposite: a single white volume, boxy shape, permeated with reflective glazing, industrial materials, faux-stone ceramics, and large, non-hierarchical open spaces, barren of any connection to the outdoors. I was attuned to a context of nostalgic countryside atmosphere; they legitimately aspired to something else—an urban, supposedly modern way of living.

Their references were neither sentimental nor objective. They were purely shaped by casual observations of renderings in real estate brochures, and by new houses in their surroundings, where novel ways of building had become systematic since the early 2000s. In a course of three decades, the cultural shift from rural to post-rural produced a crisis in identity; and, furthermore, a destitution of architectural language and references. Wider access to higher education has fostered in younger generations a sense of social and intellectual advancement beyond the contexts of their parents. Being post-rural wasn't enough anymore. Some architects, partially coming from those same communities, appropriated a grammar of an attempted modernity, enhanced by seductive images of *famous* minimalist projects but without the technical or cultural resources to match them. The results are

hybrid, confused copies failing to reach the coherence of the originals.¹ Nonetheless, these new houses generated a perception of cosmopolitanism for the locals. Designing them, or even more important, *living in them*, would make the participants to feel part of a metropolitan condition — despite of continuing to have chicken coops and flocks of sheep adjacent to their backyards.

How could I position myself in relation to that reasoning gap, that referential incompatibility? I considered politely refusing the commission. If not, would it be ethical to either force my view upon them, or allow theirs to be imposed on mine? I realized that, in order to advance, we would need a common language, perhaps achieved through sketching during the meetings. One that would allow us to mediate through our references, archetypes, and visual sources —especially one that could reconnect them with their own memories and sense of that place, which, in a way, were still the same as mine.

Keywords: architectural language; aesthetic meanings; referential system;

¹ Pedro Duarte BENTO, "Architectural Counterfeit—The art of bad copying", Journal COTAA n.2, 'The Double', Romania, 2025, pp. 309-328